

ENHANCING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN LOCAL ENERGY COMMUNITIES: A CASE STUDY ON OPTIMIZATION-DRIVEN FLEXIBILITY

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, there has been a growing acknowledgment of the vital significance of energy flexibility within local energy communities (LECs) as a fundamental strategy to optimize the utilization of a diverse array of available resources. At the district level, where flexibility is indispensable for the efficient operation of controllable assets within centralized substations, energy storage systems (ESSs) emerge as central players in achieving this objective. The primary aims encompass reducing electricity costs and maximizing the self-consumption of interconnected renewable energy systems (RES) within LECs, all while ensuring the secure and efficient operation of substation components. This challenge involves translating these objectives into a nonlinear optimization problem. Numerous optimization techniques have been explored and validated in this pursuit, applied on a real data for the heating demand of the ENVIPARK energy district in Turin, Italy. For this regard, a virtual scenario was constructed, suggesting the installation of two key energy storage technologies: battery electric storage system (BESS) and sensible thermal energy storage (TES). As a long-term assessment, the impact of energy flexibility margin, specifically BESS state of charge (SOC) and TES maximum temperature, has been accurately evaluated and quantified. Essentially, adjusting BESS SOC lower limit from 50 % to 10 % and the variation interval of the TES maximum temperature from 15 °C to 20 °C led to a substantial improvement of up to 13.9 % in energy costs. Which underscores the central role of the optimization-driven energy flexibility in reducing the heating expenses of local energy communities.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

In recent years, local energy communities (LECs) have gained prominence as hubs of sustainable energy generation, integrating diverse renewable energy sources (RES) and distributed energy assets. However, the intermittent nature of RES, coupled with dynamic energy demands, has underscored the necessity for flexible energy management strategies. This imperative arises from the pursuit of not only enhancing the efficient utilization of available local energy resources but also mitigating energy expenses, reducing electricity costs, and maximizing the integration of RES within LECs. At the heart of this challenge lies the optimization of energy storage systems (ESSs) and controllable assets within centralized substations, where safety and efficiency are paramount. Thus, the quest for energy flexibility within LECs is driven by the dual goals of sustainability and economic viability, positioning it as a crucial means to navigate the complexities of modern energy ecosystems.

1.2 Previous works

Recent studies have emphasized the importance of ESS in reducing operational costs, optimizing the use of RES, and promoting local energy generation and consumption. A study on a LEC in Valencia, Spain, evaluated the impact of a battery electric storage system (BESS) with different capacities and

ownership options, highlighting the role of storage in optimizing community energy systems (Manso-Burgos and Ribó-Pérez, 2022). Results indicate that with optimized ESS management, economic and environmental targets can be fulfilled, with a 75% residential participation, 25% of energy self-consumption was reached with 75% reduction in gas house emissions (GHG). However, the study also highlighted some limitations, including the need for optimization-based energy management to achieve such optimal results. Furthermore, research has demonstrated that energy communities can achieve significant cost savings, up to 29%, through the strategic use of ESS (Ghaemi and Anvari-Moghaddam, 2023). These findings underscore the critical role of ESS in enabling LEC to integrate RES, improving grid stability, and reducing energy costs. Weckesser et al. (2021) presented a study on optimizing the sizing and operation of photovoltaic (PV) and BESS in LEC, analyzing their impact on distribution grids and proposing strategies for grid integration and sustainability. The study reported a levelized cost of electricity of 0.25€/kWh in the village grid with a large consumer, while optimal PV and BESS capacities in the city grid with a supermarket were 189kW and 163kWh, respectively. However, the study acknowledges limitations in potentially overlooking interesting configurations due to the vast number of possible setups. Additionally, the study was not validated on the optimal sizing of PV and BESS which has an impact on the expected capital expenditure (CAPEX) costs. Tostado-V'eliz et al. (2023) proposed a novel stochastic-robust model for optimizing prosumer participation in LECs, emphasizing the benefits of ESS assets, incentives, and competitive energy pricing for efficient energy trading and cost savings. The proposed method resulted in an 84% increase in exportable capacity, an 86% reduction in electricity bills, and emphasized the role of incentives and competitive pricing in optimizing prosumer participation within energy communities. Additionally, the model showcased a 25% increase in the economic objective function with a 50% growth in robustness parameter. However, limitations were pointed out in the study including overlooking individual user interests in favor of community welfare and reliance on deterministic models that may not accurately capture uncertainties in RES generation and demand variations. Prasad Koirala et al. (2018) proposed an integrated community energy system, which involves various RES, ESS technologies, demand-side management, and community engagement. The proposed method led to significant cost savings, with studies showing up to a 37% reduction in life-cycle costs compared to individual household applications. Additionally, research indicates that community ESS can have a capacity of up to several megawatt-hours, enabling substantial contributions to LEC balancing and flexibility. Though, the study highlighted some limitations including challenges in aligning conflicting expectations of various stakeholders, such as LEC and system operators, and the need to address uncertainties in price and load forecasts for revenue maximization. It is worth noting that all previous studies did not investigate the impact of the ESS operation margins and the optimized control of hybrid ESSs (HESS) that gather thermal energy storage (TES) and BESS in one system. In LEC centralized substation, such systems need to consider the difference in dynamic between electric and thermal storage technologies during coordinated control.

1.3 The objective of this study

This study addresses the challenges mentioned earlier by implementing a cyclic optimization-driven control of HESS in a central substation of LEC. The goal is to take advantage of the available expendable flexibility boundaries of HESS to reach short- and long-terms targets i.e., dealing with hourly electricity price fluctuations, RES intermitted behavior and seasonal weather deviations. In this context, this article presents a simulation study based on a virtual scenario to assess the impact of an optimization-driven HESS to fulfill the heating demand of ENVIPARK research facility in Turin. This study proposes a hybridization architecture of HESS sub-systems implemented in a centralized heating substation. HESS assembles BESS and TES which is a large stratified water tank. HESS is driven on an hourly basis by adjusting the operation point of the main heat source, which is, an air-source heat pump (HP), and the charging/discharging rate of BESS. This is achieved thanks to a nonlinear constrained optimization algorithm. The optimization aims to decrease the heating energy cost, maximizing the RES self-share of the existing PV system, while satisfying the technical constraints of HESS. The difference in system dynamics between the two energy storage technologies is also addressed.

2 METHOD

This section presents and explains the optimization-based control of HESS for LEC energy management. First, the proposed hybridization architecture is presented and explained. Then, the mathematical models of the involved systems in HESS are defined, which will be the basis for the simulation study later. Using the developed models, the nonlinear optimization algorithm will be formulated. Finally, the use-case specifications used for validation will be described, highlighting the virtual scenario that is going to be implemented in simulation.

2.1 Proposed HESS Hybridization Architecture

Based on the use-case specifications, which will be described at the end of this section, this study proposes the hybridization architecture shown in Figure 1. It consists of TES fed by an air-source HP. The HP compressor is powered by a combination of BESS and a PV system in addition to the low-voltage grid. Two main controllable assets are adopted to implement the optimization-based control of HESS, which are HP and BESS. For the first one, a variable speed compressor is needed to adjust continuously the refrigerant flow, and consequently, the HP sink temperature level. For the second one, a DC-to-AC inverter/charger is needed to interface BESS with the local AC bus and control the charging/discharging rates. However, this study does not include any optimal sizing of these sub-systems and the related investment cost is excluded from the final evaluation.

Figure 1: Simple overview of the connection topology of HESS in the centralized heating substation

2.2 System modelling

Heat pump coefficient of performance (COP)

For HP, COP is defined based on the source and sink temperatures as described in (1), where T_{source} and T_{sink} are respectively the source (outdoor temperature) and sink temperatures [Kelvin]. In this study, we assume that HP sink temperature can be approximated to be the condenser temperature for simplicity. η_{HP} is an empirical coefficient that calibrates the ideal COP (Carnot COP) to the real one, in our case, it is fixed to 0.15.

$$COP = \eta_{HP} \frac{T_{sink}}{T_{sink} - T_{source}} \quad (1)$$

The consumed electricity P_{el_HP} [kW], related to a supplied HP heat Q_{HP_out} [kW] is formulated in (2). It is mainly related to compressor operation.

$$P_{el_HP} = \frac{Q_{HP_out}}{COP} \quad (2)$$

Ideally, the heat consumed by HPs in the evaporation process is formulated in (3) (neglecting heat wastes in the HP sub-units):

$$Q_{HP_in} = Q_{HP_out} - P_{el_HP} \quad (3)$$

As it will be explained later, Q_{HP_in} is nothing but the heat extracted from outdoor environment [kW].

Stratified water tank temperature

Regarding TES, a stratified multi-node model water tank is adopted. The differential equation for the evaluation of water temperature in one node i in the water tank is formulated in (4):

$$m_i C_p \frac{dT_i}{dt} = Q_{IN,i} - Q_{OUT,i} + Q_{COND,i} + Q_{CONV,i} - Q_{LOSS,i} \quad (4)$$

Where $Q_{IN,i}$ and $Q_{OUT,i}$ are respectively the supplied and extracted heat at the node i [kW]. In this study, this applies only to the first node ($i=1$); m_i is the water mass of layer i [kg]; C_p is the water specific heat (4182 J/kg.°C). $Q_{CONV,i}$ is the heat power [kW] gained or lost via convection mode at the node i . it is formulated as below:

$$Q_{CONV,i} = \chi_{UP} \cdot (m_{IN} - m_{OUT}) \cdot C_p \cdot (T(i-1) - T(i)) - \chi_{DOWN} \cdot (m_{OUT} - m_{IN}) \cdot C_p \cdot (T(i) - T(i+1)) \quad (5)$$

Where m_{IN} and m_{OUT} are respectively the inlet and outlet water flows [kg/s]; χ_{UP} and χ_{DOWN} are respectively the flow direction indicators:

$$\chi_{UP} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } m_{IN} > m_{OUT} \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}, \quad \chi_{DOWN} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } m_{OUT} > m_{IN} \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$Q_{COND,i}$ is the heat transferred to or from layer i via conduction mode [kW], it is formulated as below:

$$Q_{COND,i} = \frac{k \cdot A}{dX} (T(i-1) - T(i)) - \frac{k \cdot A}{dX} (T(i) - T(i+1)) \quad (7)$$

Where k is the thermal conductivity of water (0.598 W/m.K), A is the cross-section area of the water [m²]; dX is the node (water layer) thickness [m].

$Q_{LOSS,i}$ is the heat loss through the tank metal wall in layer i [kW], it is formulated as below:

$$Q_{LOSS,i} = kW \cdot U \cdot (T(i) - T_{AMB}) \quad (8)$$

Where kW is thermal conductivity of the wall (2.5 J/m².°C); U is the water node lateral surface [m²];

and T_{AMB} is the ambient temperature, chosen 23 °C.

To update the water temperature at each node, the differential equation is solved numerically using the equation below:

$$\Delta T(i) = \frac{\Delta t}{Cp \cdot \rho \cdot \pi \cdot R^2 \cdot dX} (Q_{COND,i} + Q_{CONV,i} - Q_{LOSS,i}) \quad (9)$$

Where $\Delta T(i)$ is the temperature incrementation at layer i [° C]; ρ is the water density [kg/m³]; R is the diameter of the water cross-section area in the tank [m].

BESS state of charge (SOC)

BESS SOC level for the next time interval is estimated via the following equation:

$$SOC(t + \Delta T) = SOC(t) - 100 \cdot \frac{I_B \cdot \Delta T}{C} \quad (10)$$

$SOC(t)$ is the measured value [%] while $SOC(t + \Delta T)$ is the predicted one at the time horizon ΔT ; C is the BESS rated capacity [Ah] and I_B is the running current [A] which is calculated thanks to the next simple equation:

$$I_B = \frac{P_B}{V_B} \quad (11)$$

V_B is the BESS voltage [72 V], for simplicity it is considered constant (three 24V units in series); P_B is the exchanged BESS power [W], it takes positive value in case of charging and negative values in case of discharging. For simplicity, BESS self-discharge process is not modeled.

2.3 Nonlinear optimization

In this study, Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP) is chosen as an optimizer for the optimization problem, it is an approach that starts with an initial guess for the decision variables x . At each time step, it forms a quadratic approximation of the Lagrangian, which is the objective function $f(x)$ combined with a weighted sum of the constraint functions $h(x)$ and $g(x)$, and find the optimal solution in an iterative way (Boggs et al., 1995).

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & f(x) = \frac{1}{2} x^T Q x + F^T x \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & g(x) \leq 0 \\ & h(x) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$L(x, \lambda) = f(x) - \lambda^T h(x) - v^T g(x) \quad (13)$$

Q and F are respectively the quadratic cost matrix and the linear cost vector; λ is a vector of Lagrangian multipliers for the equality constraints; v is a vector of Lagrangian multipliers for the inequality constraints.

The problem is then shifted from minimizing $f(x)$ to minimizing $L(x, \lambda, v)$ which holds the objective function along with the constraints. The optimization algorithm iteratively updates the decision variables x , Lagrange multipliers λ and v until convergence. The goal is to find an x that minimizes the Lagrangian subject to the constraints.

The objective function adopted in this study is formulated as follow:

$$J = \begin{cases} EP_i \cdot \left(\frac{Q_{HP,i}}{COP_i} - P_{B,i} - P_{PV,i} \right) & \text{if } EP_i > EP_{TH} \\ \left(\frac{Q_{HP,i}}{COP_i} - P_{B,i} - P_{PV,i} \right)^2 & \text{if } EP_i \leq EP_{TH} \end{cases} + \sigma_{MAX} (T_i - T_{MAX})^2 + \sigma_{MIN} (T_i - T_{MIN})^2 \quad (14)$$

Subject to the hard constrain formulated below:

$$SOC_{MIN} \leq SOC_i - 100 \cdot \frac{I_{B,i} \cdot \Delta T}{C} \leq SOC_{MAX} \quad (15)$$

Where EP_i is the electricity price at time step i [€/kWh]; EP_{TH} is the electricity price threshold (here chosen 0.06 €/kWh); $Q_{HP,i}$ is the supplied HP heat power at time step i [kW]; $P_{B,i}$ is the exchanged BESS power at time step i [kW]; $P_{PV,i}$ is the supplied PV power at time step i [kW]; COP_i is the HP coefficient of performance level at time step i [-]; T_{MAX} is the maximum TES water temperature [°C] while T_i is the water temperature at time step i [°C]; SOC_{MIN} and SOC_{MAX} are respectively the minimum and maximum BESS SOC control limits [%]; SOC_i is SOC level at time step i and $I_{B,i}$ is the BESS charging or discharging current at time step i .

σ_{MAX} and σ_{MIN} are respectively the weighting coefficients of the upper and lower TES maximum water temperature constraint, it is expressed as below:

$$\sigma_{MAX} = \begin{cases} 100 & \text{if } T_i > T_{MAX} \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (16.a)$$

$$\sigma_{MIN} = \begin{cases} 100 & \text{if } T_i < T_{MIN} \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (16.b)$$

The objective function has two formulas according to the electricity price value, when the electricity price is lower than a predefined threshold EP_{TH} , the optimization aims to increase the PV power self-consumption so the dependency to the grid is minimized. When the electricity price is higher than this threshold, the optimizer pushes more into selling extra PV power to the grid utility.

2.4 Use-case description

The Live-in Lab ENVIPARK consists of ten buildings, four of which are mainly used as laboratories, five as offices and one as a canteen and restaurant. Total capacity: district heating network is supplied by two heat exchangers with 1.2 MW each. Temperature levels: supply temperature for winter air conditioning is around 75°C during the winter season. Supply temperature for domestic heat water (DHW) production is around 45°C. There is also a natural gas back-up generator with a thermal power of 1 MW. DHW is produced locally in each building of the premises through HPs with electric power of 700W and thermal power of 1950 W. Totally there are eight HPs dedicated to DHW production. All the thermal systems (generators, heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC), pumps) are controlled through a BMS. Type of end-user connections/terminals: radiators, fan coils, air vents connected to HVAC on 16.7 KWp PV system; 470 KWp hydropower plant.

Figures 2 and 3 show respectively the electric and heating networks installed in the facility. In this study, we focus solely on the electric and heating energy flows. Disaggregated data related to the energy consumption at each individual buildings are excluded from this study as the focus is on the aggregated energy consumption of the whole facility, therefore, we exclusively use data registered in the main energy meters installed in the district heating (DH) heat exchanger and at each electric transformer.

Figure 2: Electric power distribution in the ENVIPARK research facility

Figure 3: Heating distribution network in ENVIPARK

To validate the proposed optimization-based heating management of ENVIPARK LEC, this study admits the existence of a set of hardware in the facility heating substation as Figure 1 shows. The current heating system at ENVIPARK is based on using the urban DH network via a heat exchanger without the use of any ESS technology. This scenario makes it meaningful to assess the impact of adding ESS on the overall park LEC heating cost. Therefore, this study suggests the use of an air-source HP for heating instead of DH, which makes it possible the integration of RES, such as the existing PV systems along with the suggested BESS and TES. However, the hydro-plant generated energy available in the park is excluded as it is continuously feeding power to the grid utility.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, a detailed simulation study, using the system and methods described in Section 2, is carried out. First, system parameters, mainly related to the district's main substation, are listed. This includes also the analysis of the one year validation data, which is PV production and heat load patterns of the facility. At the end of the section, detailed case-to-case assessments are given regarding the optimized control of HESS.

3.1 System parameters and method validation environment

As stated earlier, the current heating energy source is the urban DH, data related to the DH energy consumption during 2019 was used for validation. For this purpose, hourly data measurement collected from the energy meter installed on the main DH heat exchanger was used. This data shows high energy consumption in winter with relatively high fluctuations (see Figure 4(a)). The summer period shows low and stable energy consumption related mainly to DHW needs. Moreover, the hourly power

production of PV system during the same year is displayed in Figure 4 (b), in which, considerable energy was produced during summer and mid-season periods. As the energy optimization method relies on the dynamic price of electricity, the electricity annual data displayed in Figure 4 (c) was used. In real case, the electricity price, managed by the grid utility, changes in yearly-basis only, we came to the assumption of adopting hourly dynamic price to give more challenging management mission to the energy optimizer. System parameters, used for simulation, are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. System parameters

System	Parameter	Value
TES	Volume	3 m ³
	Inlet flow	0.6 kg/s
	Outlet flow	0.4 kg/s
PV	PV peak power	16 kWp
ESS	Voltage	72 V
	Capacity	550 Ah
	Power	15 kW
HP	Capacity	50 kW
	Supply temperature range	[45°C - 65 °C]

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4: Simulation conditions (a) heat load (b) PV power (c) electricity price

This study assesses the long-term impact of two main flexibility criteria, which are the TES maximum temperature and the BESS SOC limits. For this regard, two scenarios with two different operation flexibility limits are considered, Scenario 1 which is formulated in (17.a) and Scenario 2 which is formulated in (17.b).

$$50\% \leq SOC \leq 90\% \quad (17.a)$$

$$50^\circ\text{C} \leq T_{\max} \leq 65^\circ\text{C}$$

$$10\% \leq SOC \leq 90\% \quad (17.b)$$

$$45^\circ\text{C} \leq T_{\max} \leq 65^\circ\text{C}$$

Below, the simulation results of the optimization-driven HESS using SQP are displayed. Hourly data for the optimal values of the decision variables are shown in Figures 5 and 6 for the two operation scenarios. The HP condenser temperature is more dynamic in the case of Scenario 2 compared to Scenario 1 due to the reason of the extended operation margins of TES and BESS. Moreover, the BESS power show more fluctuating patterns during summer and mid-season to make it possible managing locally the considerable produced PV energy. In real operation scenarios, decision variables are the setpoints to be defined by a higher energy management level. It is worth mentioning that real systems cannot ideally follow the setpoints as they are subject to response time delays. This concern is clearly visible in the case of HPs because the condenser temperature needs up to few minutes to reach the desired value. This is due to the thermal energy transfer process and to the internal temperature regulation in HP. For BESS, reaching the power setpoint is a matter of milliseconds only due to the fast dynamic of the electric phenomenon. However, as the main goal of this study is the long-term assessment of HESS optimal control, we assume that HP and BESS are showing ideal setpoint tracking.

Figure 5: HP condenser temperature setpoint: (a) with flexibility Scenario 1 (b) with flexibility Scenario 2

Figure 6: BESS power setpoint: (a) with flexibility Scenario 1 (b) with flexibility Scenario 2

Figure 7: HP supplied heat: (a) with flexibility Scenario 1 (b) with flexibility Scenario 2

Figure 7 shows how the optimization pushes HP to operate up to higher levels in winter. This is due to the need to cover the heating energy demand which is significant in winter. Due to the extended HESS flexibility in Scenario 2, HP heat supply shows more fluctuated pattern caused by the objective function minimization process. As Figure 8 shows, with both optimization scenarios, BESS tends to operate with lower SOC levels in winter due to the lack of extra PV powers. During summer and sunny days, the optimizer uses BESS flexibility to store extra PV power when optimizing the heating cost. Due to the chosen high BESS capacity (550 Ah), SOC variation dynamic is relatively slower, which explains the time needed to reach both max and min SOC limits. However, operating BESS with low SOC values for long periods may accelerate the BESS degradation and decrease their life-time.

Figure 8: BESS SOC variation: (a) with flexibility scenario 1 (b) with flexibility scenario 2

Figure 9: TES maximum water temperature: (a) with flexibility Scenario 1 (b) with flexibility Scenario 2

Figure 9 shows the hourly variation of TES water maximum temperature for both optimization scenarios. In contrast to the BESS SOC constraint, this one was formulated as a soft inequality constraint as described in (14), which explains why both operation scenarios show slight constraint violations several times over the year. The reason behind choosing soft constraints for TES maximum water temperature instead of hard formulation (such as BESS SOC constraint) was related to the need to provide additional flexibility to the optimizer as those limits were not supposed to be strictly satisfied at each time step. Table 2 shows a comparative assessment of several optimization algorithms validated on the same simulation data. This assessment includes the electricity cost evaluation related to the annual heating demand in 2019 for the whole ENVIPARK facility and the execution time of each optimization algorithm. The heating cost in this case is calculated using the dynamic price illustrated in Figure 4 (c) and the electric power imported from the grid for each scenario. The table shows how significant is the impact of extending the operation flexibility boundaries given to each ESS technology (TES and BESS) in the performance of the heating cost optimization. Adjusting the variation interval of the TES maximum water temperature from 10°C to 15°C and BESS SOC variation interval from 40% to 80% has led to a cost saving of up to 12.4% using SQP chosen in this article, and 13.9% using pattern search algorithm. However, extended flexibility limits have led to more computing time, which is explained by the prolonged search space for each algorithm. If the energy cost optimization process is a part of real-time control, this issue is a crucial and should be considered.

Table 2. Flexibility impact assessment of different optimization methods

Optimization algorithm	Heating cost		Execution time		Cost saving (Baseline Scenario 1)
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	
SQP	1466 €	1284 €	8 min	12 min	12.4%
Interior-point (Capitanescu et al., 2007)	1456 €	1262 €	22 min	28 min	13.3%
Active-set (Zhong et al., 2023)	1468 €	1290 €	6 min	7 min	12.1%
Pattern search (Tao et al., 2021)	1434 €	1234 €	1.7 hour	1.6 hour	13.9%

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study explores an integration and operation solution of a hybrid energy storage system into an energy community as a part of a centralized heating system. This study suggests fulfilling the heating demand using an air-source heat pump instead of the district heating network to make it possible to integrate renewables and electric storage technologies. The focus was on the hourly optimal control of the heat pump and the batteries inverter/charger. This simulation study shows a long-term assessment of the cyclic optimization-driven heating system, and the impact of the operation flexibility margins on the cost optimization performance. Validation on real data demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed framework, particularly maximizing the photovoltaic self-share energy during summer. Comparative analysis of different optimization algorithms showcases mixed performances in providing cost-effective heating with less computing times.

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